

FREE ELECTROMAGNETIC OSCILLATIONS (CIRCUIT OF OSCILLATION). ENERGY CHANGE IN THE VIBRATION CONTOUR

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ANNOTATION

In this article free electromagnetic oscillations (oscillation circuit). problems related to energy changes in the vibration contour are given.

Key words: capacitor, constant current, inductive coil, electrical resistance, electromagnetic oscillations

АННОТАЦИЯ

В этой статье о свободных электромагнитных колебаниях (колебательный контур). приведены задачи, связанные с изменением энергии в контуре вибрации.

Ключевые слова: конденсатор, постоянный ток, катушка индуктивности, электрическое сопротивление, электромагнитные колебания.

Simple electromagnetic oscillations can be generated in an electrical circuit consisting of a capacitor and an inductive coil. Let's build an electric circuit consisting of a capacitor, an inductive coil, a constant current source and a switch (Fig. 1.1). For simplicity, we do not take into account the electrical resistance of the circuit. When the connector is connected to the left, the capacitor plates S are charged from the battery. In this case, an electric field with maximum energy is formed between the capacitor covers

Then we connect the disconnecter to the right, in this case, the charged capacitor is connected to the coil L. Let's take a closer look at the next step (Figure 3.2).

1.1-rasm.

Figure 1.2.

The upper cover of the capacitor is positive, and the lower cover is charged in a negative direction, so it remains a source of current (case 1). As a result, charges move from the positive cover of the capacitor through the inductive coil to the negative cover, that is, a current is created. A magnetic field is formed around this current. This current gradually increases and reaches its maximum value due to the inductance of the coil (see the graph in the figure).

The magnetic field created around the current passing through the coil is also increasing (case 2). In this case, the energy of the electric field between the capacitor covers is reduced to zero. The energy of the magnetic field around the coil increases and reaches its maximum value W_m . It is known from the previous topics that according to the phenomenon of electromagnetic induction, an induction voltage v_u occurs in a coil located in a changing magnetic field. As the current decreases, the induced voltage

charges the capacitor in the opposite direction compared to the previous one (case 3). The charged capacitor again generates a current through the inductive coil (case 4). This current is also increasing, and the magnetic field created by it creates an induction voltage in the coil. As the current decreases, the induced voltage recharges the capacitor (case 5). In case 5 and case 1, the signs of the capacitor charge are the same. Therefore, the next processes will continue in the same sequence as before.

We draw the following conclusions from the considered processes:

1. In a circuit consisting of a capacitor and an inductive coil, a charge given to the capacitor from a constant current source creates an alternating current in a closed circuit.
2. Initially, the energy received from the source is collected as electric field energy between the capacitor covers, and then it is converted into magnetic field energy around the coil. Then magnetic field energy, electric field energy, etc. rotates periodically.

In class 10 it was said that any repetitive process is called vibration. Therefore, the process in the circuit consisting of a capacitor and a coil has an oscillatory character. It is called electromagnetic vibrations. In the coil (L) and capacitor (C) where the electromagnetic vibrations are generated is called a closed chain oscillation circuit

(3.3-rasm).

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Periodically in the circuit when electromagnetic oscillations occur as electric field energy turns into magnetic field energy and vice versa. In an ideal vibration circuit, there is no energy dissipation, so the vibrations do not die out. Full energy is conserved and its value at any instant is:

$$q^2 / 2C + Li^2 / 2$$

$$W = + = m = m = \text{const.}$$

$$2C \quad 2C \quad 2$$

Here: L is the inductance of the coil, C is the capacitance of the capacitor, i and Im are the instantaneous and maximum values of the current, respectively, and q and qm are the instantaneous and maximum values of the charge in the capacitor, respectively.

In the oscillating circuit, the energy of the electric field in the capacitor turns into the energy of the magnetic field in the coil and vice versa. . Accordingly, we present the similarity between the parameters of mechanical and electrical vibrations in the table below.

Mechanical quantities. Electrical quantities

x - coordinate q - charge

u - speed i - current

m - mass L - inductance

k is the stiffness of the spring and 1/C is the inverse of the capacity

$kx^2/2$ – potential energy $q^2/(2C)$ – electric field energy

$mu^2/2$ – kinetic energy $Li^2/2$ – magnetic field energy

It should be noted that although electromagnetic and mechanical vibrations are of different nature, they are represented by similar equations.

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